

Research Article

Allride Application

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Abstract: *Transportation is one of the main components of the tourism industry. Transportation is necessary for individuals to move from one location to another attraction so that they can enjoy the activities there. The development of the AllRide app primarily concentrates on transportation issues. The main objective of this application is to provide multifunctional transportation applications that cater to diverse user demands, offering economical and safe transportation alternatives as transportation costs can put a strain on tourists' budgets. Furthermore, the AllRide app gives customers thorough information about the local transport network to have access to affordable and convenient transportation options beyond taxis by providing a variety of forms of transportation, such as buses, trains, and bicycles, facilitating travel planning and the exploration of genuine local activities for both visitors and locals. Lastly, this application commercializes through social media, marketing strategies, and reward and discount programmes to motivate users to check out the many transportation alternatives available to experience the advantages.*

Keywords: Transportation, Variety, Local, Tourism Industry

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1. INTRODUCTION

Transportation is one of the main components of the tourism industry. Transportation is necessary for individuals to move from one location to another attraction, so that they can enjoy the activities there. There are different modes of transportation in tourism, including airplanes, ferries, taxis, buses, vans, monorails, LRT, and others. In today's modern era, many individuals utilize mobile devices to help them with daily tasks such as finding public transport. Recently the use of E-hailing has become an important mode of transportation, due to the emergence of E-hailing it has become an important part for transportation. For example, Grab, Agoda, Maxim and others. The presence of AllRide emphasizes the importance of technology in serving the requirements of today's travelers. Using this app not only provides convenience but also contributes to the Malaysian government's efforts to boost domestic tourism and establish Malaysia as a top tourist destination. From a market perspective, AllRide's development is being encouraged by Malaysia's thriving tourist economy and growing awareness of technology's role in travel. AllRide has the potential to lead the Malaysian transportation app industry by focusing on quality and dependability, benefiting both passengers and the local tourism sector.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

DISPLAY IN ALLRIDE APPLICATIONS	DESCRIPTION/ EXPLANATION
	<p>This is the the home page of our application when you click to open the app</p>
	<p>This page shows some of the choices that user can choose which one of deals they wanted to use</p>

		<p>This page shows how to book the flight ticket by using the apps. For booking the flight ticket, they have provided the departure point to the arrival destination. They also provide the date of departure and the return time.</p>
		<p>This page show what the payment method which is available in the application</p>
		<p>This page allows the user to pick their current location to another destination. The price will be based on the distance from their pickup location to their destination.</p>

	<p>This page shows the app provides train information, schedules, and route planning for train journeys. It helps users find the most cost-effective options and plan their trip effectively.</p>
	<p>This page provides users with real - time estimated fares for selected dates of buses schedule.</p>

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Novelty and Uniqueness

Allride's dedication to enabling local small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) is an important aspect of its innovation. Despite competing applications, which frequently rely on major international companies, Allride encourages collaboration with local SMEs. This approach benefits local economies while also creating a sense of community and empowerment in local enterprises. Through adding local SMEs on its platform, Allride makes sure that economic advantages are distributed more evenly across the community. Local transportation businesses, such as taxis, cars, trains, and bike rentals, are given a platform to compete and expand. This method helps to sustain and expand small enterprises, giving them a consistent source of income and potential for growth.

3.2. Benefit to Economy, Environment and Social

Allride has a substantial influence on the economy, the environment, and social landscape by creating employment and supporting local SMEs, resulting in higher individual earnings and company growth. It improves transportation efficiency by lowering jams and gas expenditures. Environmentally, Allride encourages eco-friendly modes of transportation such as bicycles, which reduces greenhouse gas emissions while improving air quality. Socially, it enhances communities by providing a variety of economical transportation alternatives, increasing accessibility, and assuring safety. Overall, Allride promotes sustainable urban life, economic development, and social well-being.

3.3 Potential commercialization

AllRide can enhance its presence and engagement on social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and Twitter by employing strategies like creating engaging content, collaborating with influencers, running user-generated content campaigns with branded hashtags, and utilizing paid advertising to target potential users. Additionally, AllRide should actively engage with followers, respond quickly to queries, and build community through regular updates. The marketing strategy involves analyzing the transportation industry, identifying market segments, and understanding consumer needs to craft a competitive approach using social media, online advertising, and partnerships with local businesses while continuously measuring performance data. AllRide's Reward and Discount Program incentivizes users to explore different transportation options by offering reward points or discounts, enhancing user loyalty and encouraging exploration of the app's offerings (De & De, 2023).

4. DISCUSSION

The outcomes of this research have provided insight into the novelty and uniqueness of the Allride application, which benefits both individuals and operators. Combining all modes of transportation allows individuals to become drivers and interact with passengers. Also, by assisting local businesses and providing a platform for them to grow. Furthermore, studies indicate that using the AllRide application can help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate the negative effects of climate change. By encouraging the use of public transportation and ride sharing, we can help to reduce traffic congestion and preserve the urban environment. Finally, these applications can improve local communities' well-being by increasing mobility and making it easier to access essential services like employment, education, healthcare, and social activities.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, AllRide is more than just an app but it is a game-changer for urban transportation. By promoting bicycles, electric vehicles, and other green solutions, AllRide is not just reducing emissions; it is also paving the way for healthier, more vibrant cities. With a commitment to inclusivity, safety, and affordability, AllRide believes that the future is within reach, showcasing how innovation and sustainability can join forces to build a better world for all. As we look to the future, AllRide exemplifies how it represents a step towards a future where technology and sustainability work together to create a better world for everyone.

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